

Augmented Reality for Live Performances Feasibility Study

Research Report

Shuuto.

Project Lead (author): Julian Norum
Research Assistant: Ka Sonn Tang
Research Assistant: Benjamin Bartnes

Consultant Shutoo AS: Arne Berggren
Consultant Shuuto AS: Viktor Enoksen

Consultant Nord University: Andrew Mark Brownridge
Consultant Nord University: Kristian Egge

External Consultant: Joachim Voldseth

For a short visual breakdown of the test-case produced this study, please refer to the video breakdown ([Norum, 2020a](#)). In the video summary, experimentation is largely omitted, while more details are included in this report.

A list of apps and plugins utilized can be found in the appendix.

Table of Contents:

[1. Introduction:](#)

[2. Summary](#)

[3. Photogrammetry](#)

[4. Concept Sculpt and Model](#)

[5. Facial Capture](#)

[6. Facial Rig](#)

[7. USDZ Conversion](#)

[8. GLB Conversion](#)

[9. Upload and Automatic Device Detection](#)

[10. QR-code and Marketing Example:](#)

[11. Final AR-experience](#)

[12. Suggestions for further research:](#)

[13. Conclusion:](#)

1. Introduction:

The study presents a test-case in the form of a ghostly character for AR, developed for the IP “Miriam”, by production company Shuuto Midt AS. The test-case is designed as additional Augmented Reality (AR) content, in relation to the marketing of a theatre performance in 2021. More importantly, the test-case aids to survey possibilities with current standards, while pointing to future potentials of AR, particularly in anticipation of immersive AR-hardware such as the awaited Apple Glasses (Rossignol, 2019). The aim of the study is to gauge the feasibility of AR-technology for enhanced set design and virtual characters, in live performances.

As such, the study assesses the grounds for continued research efforts, as the “Miriam” IP is projected to be performed in Nidaros Cathedral over a ten year period — a regular part of the festival Olavsfestdagene. This is a timeframe which facilitates long-term planning, taking future technological innovations such as AR-glasses and contact lenses into consideration. Implementation of virtual elements for live performances using real-time AR technology is not otherwise a potential for the production, and is not yet a viable commercial option for such productions in the region. The practical integration of AR in actual productions will be instrumental for empirical data collection in future studies, to measure commercial viability and Willingness to Pay (WTP).

2. Summary

The AR-content produced in the test-case needed to be accessible to audiences without the need to download an application. Apple’s novel format USDZ was therefore given main emphasis, due to its efficiency with relatively large data files. Apple’s latest lidar enhanced devices, such as the iPhone 12 and iPad Pro 2020, allow for real-time occlusion of objects and improved “scene understanding” overall. Combined with AI-generated image-based lighting (IBL), this contributed to favoring the USDZ-format. These were all elements tested in the study.

Currently, a main challenge of AR on portable devices is the lack of support for complex animation-cache data. The study documents a workflow for capturing facial-capture data using the selfie-camera on an iPhone, then transferring this data to a joint-based animation which may be exported to AR. The method is applicable to a range of complex animation that would normally rely on animation caching.

While not given emphasis in the study, an Android-compatible file was also generated, along with a custom html-code that recognizes the user’s platform. This enables the final AR-experience to be triggered from a single QR-code, which may be implemented in marketing material as intended.

3. Photogrammetry

Fig1. Piece of point cloud (left). Final merged point cloud in CloudCompare. Still from video ([Norum, 2020b](#)).

The scanning app “Capture” for the iPhone, which uses the true depth “selfie camera” (iPhone 10 or above) to generate a point cloud, was tested. While the scans were of high quality, a great limitation was that only a part of the head could be scanned at a time. Some effort was devoted to the process of generating several dense point clouds to be merged using “Cloud Compare” (Fig 1). While somewhat restricted, this process could prove an accessible way to assemble highly detailed scans without specialized equipment.

While this seemed promising, it became clear that new apps for photogrammetry, for their speed and convenience, would meet a similar visual fidelity at a fraction of the production time. Various apps available on the Apple AppStore were tested, including “Bellus 3d”, “Scandy Pro”, “Display.land” (now discontinued), and finally Trnio which provided the overall best result.

The Trnio app would not be applicable to large scale photogrammetry, but for the purpose of scanning smaller objects, it provides comparable results to more traditional methods of photogrammetry. The main difference being that the computing takes place in “the cloud” through automated steps.

Fig 2. Trnio interface (left). Example of artefact (right).

The Trnio interface provided easy access to various photogrammetry projects saved to their server. Some scanning errors would at times be apparent on parts of the color map (Fig 2.). Several scans were therefore produced and successful parts assembled in ZBrush.

Fig 3. Final photogrammetry model.

Considering the ease of use of this method compared to traditional photogrammetry, the final result is of surprisingly high quality (Fig 3). It should be noted that for accurate high-resolution scans of moving objects such as a human head, it would still be preferable with a proper light-stage setup for photogrammetry (using multiple cameras at once). For the purposes of this project, the photogrammetry would only serve as a basis for a concept sculpt, and could be more experimental. It is likely that the Trnio app, and similar future updates, may largely replace traditional photogrammetry methods for a range of projects, due to their efficiency.

4. Concept Sculpt and Model

Fig 4. Conceptual sculpt and retopology

Based on the photogrammetry model, a concept sculpt was produced in ZBrush (Fig 4). A retopologized model was also produced (based on best practices for facial capture), and fitted to the model.

Fig 5. Cross-polarized texture reference used for tertiary details (Texturing.xyz).

The model was sculpted to a tertiary stage of details. Cross polarization photography reduces glare and reflection on surfaces, and is commonly used in the VFX and game industry. Such texture data, obtained from Texturing.xyz, facilitated skin detailing (Fig. 5) In addition, details were largely sculpted “by hand”.

Fig. 6. Clothing and other elements of the model.

Clothing and other elements of the model were produced according to standard CG-art workflows (Fig. 6). The production pipeline consisted of Marvelous Designer, Maya, ZBrush, Substance Painter and Photoshop.

5. Facial Capture

The facial capture solution utilized in the project was the iPhone app Face Cap (Bannaflak, 2020). Like similar solutions, it utilizes the “true depth” capability of the selfie camera (iPhone 10 or higher) to track facial movements in real time.

FaceCap relies on a model preconfigured with 52 blendshapes (various facial expressions). Before facial capture could be attempted, these individual blendshapes needed to be produced.

Fig 7. FaceIt Plugin for Blender (left), 52 blendshapes assembled in Maya (right)

To facilitate this process, a plugin for Blender called “Faceit” (FBra. 2020) was tested in order to automatically generate the 52 blendshapes required. The plugin allowed export of blendshapes according to the FaceCap naming convention, which could then be assembled in maya (Fig 7).

This method drastically reduces production time of blend shapes. The examples provided from the developer suggests that the method can successfully be implemented for a variety of humanoid faces.

Fig 8. FaceCap app (left). FBX imported to Maya with keyframed blendshape node (right)

A simple head movement was recorded using the FaceCap app. This data could be exported from the app as an FBX file, opened in Maya (Fig 8).

Once in Maya, the keyframe values from the blendshape node of the Facecap model could simply be copied over to the corresponding blendshape nodes for our model, which had the correct order and naming convention.

Fig 9. Mouth animation test. Still-frame from video ([Norum, J. 2020c](#))

For more refined results, further optimization of the blendshapes is needed, which would require an extended production period. Especially for satisfactory mouth deformation. Some tests were done, and mouth animation technically works (Fig 9), which shows potential for actor impersonation of the virtual character in future studies. A short test of mouth animation can be seen online ([Norum, J. 2020c](#)).

Mouth animation was not included in the idle-animation for the USDZ-file. The combination of mouth movement and voice-elements would contribute greatly to the “illusion of life” in future studies.

6. Facial Rig

Complex animation data such as facial capture is usually stored in an animation cache. While there is support for such files (for instance Alembic) in game engines, these cached animations are not supported on portable devices, nor for the intended USDZ format.

Fig 10. Facial rig in Maya. Vertex-animation to joint-based animation.

To make use of the facial-capture data, a custom rig was developed in Maya, to transfer the vertex-based animation to joint based animation (Fig 10).

A custom script by Darko Bjelanović (Bjelanović, n.a.) facilitated the process somewhat, while some steps needed to be done manually. Technically, the following summarized steps in Maya could all be done manually:

- create and snap joints to the animated vertices in question
- “point on poly” constrain each joint to their corresponding vertex
- bake resulting animation to all joints
- delete by type “constraints”

These steps will effectively transfer the vertex animation to joint animation.

Fig 11. Joint hierarchy for the facial rig

The joints, which now have animation data, can then be smooth-bound to the mesh. The resulting facial animation is joint-driven, and may be exported as an FBX without the use of an animation cache.

Figure 11 shows the joint hierarchy for the facial rig. The number of joints driving the facial animation totals 876, which all exist in a group node (null1). This group node is the child of a joint controlling the head rotation (joint 2), which again is the child of the root joint (joint 1) that can be attached to the rest of the skeletal structure. In addition, there are two joints controlling eye-rotation (joint 4 & 5), whose rotational animation was also based on the FaceCap recording.

Due to the large file sizes as a consequence of the substantial amount of animated joints, the animation loop was eventually limited to 170 frames at 30 fps, exported to FBX.

7. USDZ Conversion

To convert the FBX to USDZ, various solutions were attempted. Apple's own tool for developers, *Reality Converter* (Apple, 2020) handles various formats with ease, however for longer animation loops it never managed to load the FBX on import. Simlab Composer was

another software tested, which did manage to read the FBX, but had some issues relating to correct playback of animation speeds.

The final solution became to simply upload the FBX to Sketchfab, which introduced automatic USDZ conversion of all uploaded models earlier this year (Sketchfab, 2020).

The final USDZ is compatible with iPhone 8 or above.

8. GLB Conversion

(Texture-sizes referred to as 1k and 4k measure 1024x1024 pixels and 4096x4096 pixels respectively. All texture sizes maintain a “power of two”-rule for optimization. Common pixel sizes are therefore 256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096).

While the aim of the study was to survey potentials for USDZ, some final steps were taken to implement compatibility with Android devices.

The GLTF-format is also automatically converted using Sketchfab. The GLTF can then be downloaded and converted to a GLB-file which bakes all information to a single file, not unlike the USDZ. This conversion was done using an online conversion tool by Creators 3d (Creators 3d, 2020). However, the format generates very large file-sizes compared to USDZ.

While the USDZ file contained several texture files at 4k-resolution, it resulted in a file-size of only 11,5 MB. With the same texture resolution, the GLB file was 103,4 MB, almost a ten-fold increase in data for the same visual fidelity. The textures were therefore decreased, down from 4k to 1k for the head and clothing, and further down to 512 and even some at 256. They were also further compressed using PNG compression. This resulted in a GLB-file of 11,4 MB.

The same compression was tentatively introduced to the USDZ, but it only amounted to a 1 MB reduction in file-size, so the original texture files were kept as the final solution for the USDZ. This demonstrates that the USDZ-format handles significantly higher texture resolutions for the same amount of data.

There is also a variety of efficiency by which Android devices will handle the GLB format. The experience was tested on various Android phones and seemed to cause memory lags and runtime deficiencies, in contrast to compatible Apple devices which currently offer very stable AR-experiences.

Therefore, the final solution for Android became a version without animation and with low-res textures, finally uploaded as a GLB of 6.7 MB.

9. Upload and Automatic Device Detection

The goal for the end-user experience was that no app would be required for download, but simply a quick scan of a QR-code. With the Android-solution in place, it would be preferable that both AR-experiences could be triggered from the same QR-code.

For this, an html code invoking Google's Web-AR was implemented. The following ten lines of html-code will call the necessary Web-AR elements, and contain both the USDZ and GLB files (in blue), which were uploaded to a server using FileZilla FTP:

```
<script type="module"
src="https://unpkg.com/@google/model-viewer/dist/model-viewer.min.js"></script>
<script nomodule=""
src="https://unpkg.com/@google/model-viewer/dist/model-viewer-legacy.js"></script>

<model-viewer
src="https://labethus.com/wp-content/uploads/media-from-ftp-tmp/Miriam_170Frames_optimized.glb" ar="" ar-modes="webxr scene-viewer quick-look" ar-scale="auto" camera-controls=""
alt="Miriam"
ios-src="https://labethus.com/wp-content/uploads/media-from-ftp-tmp/Full_Body_Loop_170_Frames_201125_colorGrade.usdz"
poster="https://labethus.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Miriam_preview.png"></model-viewer>
```

A QR-code was then generated to point to the site of this html, which will initially feature the “model viewer” when viewed. When the AR-icon is pressed, the proper format will be selected depending on the device.

10. QR-code and Marketing Example:

Fig 13. Example of marketing poster with QR-code

A dynamic QR-code was generated using the online service “QR Code Generator”. It simply points to a URL which contains the html-code described earlier. It may be implemented in marketing material, as in the example (Fig 13).

11. Final AR-experience

Fig 12. Final AR-experience with environment occlusion and IBL. Screenshot on iPad Pro 2020.

The final USDZ-file has been tested on various iPhones, and loads consistently on iPhone 8 and above. It was also tested on iPad Pro 2020, which automatically enables real-time occlusion of objects, as evident by the tabletop in Figure 1. This is possible due automatic 3d generation of the real environment, made possible by the implemented lidar on newer Apple devices such as iPad 2020 Pro and iPhone 12. Real-time people occlusion is also added automatically using machine learning.

Real-time Image Based Lighting (IBL) generates a spherical image map based on the visible environment, and contributes to more accurate reflections and color. This can be observed by a subtle difference in skin hue, corresponding to the on-location lighting.

The USDZ offers a notable stability on compatible iPhone models, with highly precise tracking.

12. Suggestions for further research:

With continued hardware developments for mobile AR, higher fidelity may gradually be ported to such experiences. While not explored in this study, Apple offers the “Metal” architecture for developers (Apple, n.d.), giving access to GPU accelerated graphics for iOS. However, with current technical standards, AR-content meant to be compatible with a range of portable devices would still be better suited for hard surface elements.

To successfully simulate skin, a process of sub-surface scattering is required. This is a complex calculation of light-scatter through various media, and can be used to simulate the way light would penetrate into the epidermis (evident in the rendered image on the poster). Such calculation is not yet available for AR on portable devices. A real-time approximation of this effect is currently possible with a powerful GPU such as RTX for real-time ray-tracing. It is difficult to predict when such capabilities will arrive to portable devices.

AR-content may still achieve high visual fidelity, with the use of Physically Based Rendering and Image Based Lighting, combined with environment and people occlusion — all standard AR features compatible with Apple mobile devices as of this year. However, for virtual AR characters, more time should be devoted to the artistic production itself, in order to arrive at an aesthetically satisfying result (as one can not rely on sophisticated skin rendering). The scope of this study did not allow an attempt at a final aesthetic, but that may be prerequisite to successfully measure audience engagement in future studies.

Virtual characters would more successfully be viewed at a distance (i.e: from the perspective of an audience member watching a live performance, wearing a pair of AR glasses). This may largely render nuances of facial expression redundant, allowing to emphasise larger (and less computationally expensive) ranges of motion, interacting with the real characters on set. For this, a continued study could explore the use of wireless mocap (our research group has this technology available), allowing a virtual character to interact with other actors on stage in a more expressive way. Facial capture could be implemented, but the amount of facial joints necessary to sell the illusion, given the distance to the audience, could probably be limited and optimized.

In a theatre performance setting, it is preferable for users to download a dedicated application to their devices. The AR-Kit architecture is also available for Unity applications. This means that all capabilities with the USDZ format (explored in this study) are available for more complex AR-applications. Such applications would meet fewer technical restrictions, and more complexity could be achieved.

While cached animation could be exported to Unity, these would still not be compatible for iOS projects. However, a Unity project would offer the option of obj-sequences, computationally costly yet a viable option for complex animation and simulations to be exported to AR. Another advantage is that while real-time occlusion would be supported, one could also make use of scene-recognition technology that would contribute to “merge” the virtual content with the physical set.

The facial capture technique tested in this study, using the “true depth” camera of the iPhone, may also be utilized in a setup with game engines through a real-time live link ([Faceit, 2020](#)). A head-mounted facial capture rig combined with a motion capture suit is currently being developed by our research group. As such, future studies might not only explore pre-rendered AR-content, but also “real-time” interactions in AR or VR.

13. Conclusion:

The study finds that the prospect of implementing AR in live performances is feasible and should merit continued research. This is largely due to the technical efficiency and visual quality of current AR-solutions on Apple devices, as well as continued emphasis on lidar-enhanced hardware with the sole aim of improving AR.

The accessibility and lowered cost of wireless motion and facial-capture also make complex virtual stage characters a realistic vision. The study shows that facial-capture data can be exported to AR. If further optimized and limited in scope, combined with larger and less computationally expensive ranges of motion (fewer animated joints), such content can run smoothly on newer Apple devices. Preferably in the form of an application.

Apple’s USDZ format managed to compress complex animation data, as well as several high resolution textures to a very manageable file-size. The resulting AR experience was consistent and stable on all supported Apple devices. When given the same data, the resulting GLB file for Android was approximately ten times as heavy, and had to be considerably compressed to be readable on mobile devices.

The AR tests on Android devices were inconsistent and more crude both in terms of visual fidelity, tracking and framerate. Even when opting for a simple version without animation, the Android-experience could be described as poor when compared to the animated USDZ on Apple devices.

The study suggests that continued research into complex AR in the near future, remains an emphasis on Apple’s AR-kit architecture.

References

- Apple, n.d. Framework Metal. Retrieved from:
<https://developer.apple.com/documentation/metal>
- Norum, J. 2020a. "Project Miriam - Feasibility Study 2020". Video. Retrieved from:
<https://vimeo.com/user103667864>
- Norum, J. 2020b. "Miriam Point Cloud in CloudCompare". Video. Retrieved from:
<https://vimeo.com/483292233>
- Norum, J. 2020c. "faceLaugh_1". Video. Retrieved from:
<https://vimeo.com/483277738>
- Rossignol, J. (2019). "Apple Outlines How Augmented Reality Glasses Could Overlay Points of Interest". *MacRumors*. Retrieved from:
<https://www.macrumors.com/2019/02/26/apple-glasses-patent/>
- Sketchfab, 2020. "Sketchfab adds USDZ 3d file conversion. Sketchfab blog. Retrieved from:
<https://sketchfab.com/blogs/community/sketchfab-adds-usdz-3d-file-conversion/>
- Faceit. 2020. "Motion Capture". Faceit Online Documentation. Retrieved from:
<https://faceit-doc.readthedocs.io/en/latest/capture/#live-link-face-unreal-engine>

Appendix:

List of novel apps and plugins utilized:

- Apple, 2020. "Introducing Reality Converter". Available at:
<https://developer.apple.com/news/?id=01132020>
- Bannaflak, 2020. "Face Cap". iPhone facial capture application. Available at:
<https://www.bannaflak.com/face-cap/>
- Bjelanović, D. "bD_snapToVertex". Maya custom script. Available at:
<https://www.bjeldark.com/index>
- Creators 3d, 2020. "Online 3d Viewer and GLTF Converter". Conversion tool. Available at:
<https://www.creators3d.com/online-viewer>
- FBra, 2020. Faceit - Iphonex Shape Keys And Performance Capture. Available at:
<https://blendermarket.com/products/faceit>

Girardeau-Montaut, D. “Cloud Compare”. Available at:
<https://www.danielgm.net/cc/>

Standard Cyborg. “Capture: 3D Scan Anything”. Available at:
<https://apps.apple.com/us/app/capture-3d-scan-anything/id1444183458>

Texturing.xyz. Cross polarized texture. Available at:
<https://texturing.xyz/pages/cross-polarized-photos>